

Growth, development, yield and economic efficiency of promising tomato varieties and hybrids in the conditions of samarkand region (Uzbekistan)

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Abstract. The article presents the results of experiments on the growth, development, yield and economic efficiency of tomato varieties and hybrids as a repeated crop in fields freed from grain in the summer period. The highest quality and strongest seedlings were obtained from the Morelia F1 and Lojain F1 hybrids. The varieties and hybrids that grow and develop the fastest and yield the earliest were identified as the Morelia F1 and Lojain F1 hybrids. The fruit composition of the Morelia F1 and Lojain F1 hybrids showed the highest dry matter content (6.2 and 6.0 %) and the highest carotene content (1.8 mg% and 1.7 mg%). The yield of tomatoes by variety was 32.6 - 42.5 t/ga. The highest yield - 42.5 t/ga was obtained from the Morelia F1 hybrid plants. This indicator is 30.7 % higher than the standard - Yulduz (control) variant. The highest income of 105,655,000 soums/ha and the highest profitability rate of 191.7% were obtained when growing Morelia F1 hybrid plants.

Keywords: Tomato, variety, hybrid, seedling, leaf, stem, flower, growth, development

Introduction. In Uzbekistan, great attention is paid to ensuring food security, growing vitamin products in off-season periods, and expanding the range of plants in vegetable growing [1,2]. Today, vegetable crops are grown in our Republic on 252.8 thousand hectares, melon crops on 67.5 thousand hectares, and potatoes on 113.7 thousand hectares, with a gross yield of 11 million 200 thousand; 2.5 million and 3 million 400 thousand tons, respectively [3,4]. In Uzbekistan, winter grain crops are grown on 1 million hectares of irrigated land annually [5]. After the harvest of cereal crops in June, the effective and intensive use of land, 2-3 harvests per year and additional income are an important resource for increasing vegetable cultivation in our republic [6,7].

Among vegetable crops in Uzbekistan, the most popular and widespread is tomato, which ranks first in terms of area and gross yield [8]. Tomatoes account for 40-45% of the total area of vegetable crops [6,7]. Its ripe fruit is extremely tasty, dietary, and contains various vitamins, mineral salts, organic acids and carbohydrates [8]. The biochemical composition of red tomato fruit is as follows (relative to wet weight, %): Dry matter – 6.0 - 6.6; Protein – 0.95 - 1.0; Sugar – 4.0 - 5.0; Oils – 0.2 - 0.3; Organic (malic, citric) acids – 0.5; Vitamin C (ascorbic acid) – 19 - 35 mg/%; Carotene (provitamin A) – 0.2 - 2.0 mg/%; Thiamine (V1) – 0.3 - 1.6 mg/% and Riboflavin (V2) – 1.5 - 6 mg/% [9,10,11].

Providing the population with vitamin-rich products and selecting tomato varieties and hybrids as a repeat crop in areas freed from grain in the summer are urgent tasks [12].

Purpose and objectives of the study. The purpose of the study is to study the economic and biological characteristics, quality indicators, and yield of promising tomato varieties created in Uzbekistan and imported from the Netherlands in the conditions of the Samarkand region when grown as a repeated crop in the summer period, and to provide recommendations for production.

Materials and methods. A six-variant experiment on the growth, development and yield of tomato varieties was conducted in 2022-2024 at the “Turob Bobo” farm in Tayloq district, Samarkand region.

Studies were conducted on the economic and biological characteristics, fruit quality indicators, yield and economic efficiency of promising tomato varieties and hybrids imported from the Netherlands and created in Uzbekistan (Yulduz (control); Burkhon F1; Barlos F1, Djina F1; Morelia F1 and Lojain F1). Tomato seedlings were grown in pots and planted in a permanent place on July 1 in a 70x30 cm pattern [13,14].

All agrotechnical measures, observations, measurements, analysis and calculations in the experiment were carried out based on the generally accepted methods of the All-Russian Institute of Plant Science (VIR), the Uzbek Scientific Research Institute of Vegetable and Melon Crops and Potato Growing (UzNIIOBKiK) "Methodology of conducting experiments in vegetable, melon and potato growing" (B.J. Azimov, B.B. Azimov, 2002), the Scientific Research Institute of Vegetable Farming (NIIOX) method (V.F. Belik, G.L. Bondarenko, 1979) and recommendations. The mathematical and statistical processing of yield indicators was carried out using the Microsoft Excel program using the dispersion method based on the B.A. Dospekhov method [15,16,17].

The State Register of Agricultural Crops Recommended for Planting in the Republic of Uzbekistan includes 120 varieties and hybrids for open field cultivation in 2024. Among them, there are 35 heterozygous hybrids of local varieties. In addition, the State Register includes varieties and hybrids created in the Netherlands, France, Israel, Spain, Germany, Russia, Japan and Turkey [18, 19].

Yulduz – Created in Uzbekistan. Mid-ripening, it takes 112-117 days from the time of germination of seedlings to the first ripening of fruits. The plant is simple, determinant type, medium height, medium leafy. The average weight of the fruits is 100-120 g, round shape, hard, smooth surface, very sweet taste. The dry matter content is 5.8%, the total sugar content is 3.56%, and ascorbic acid is 18.4 mg%. Tasting score is 4.2 points.

Burxon F₁ - Created in Uzbekistan. Early ripening (95-100 days), short (55-60 cm), bushy, well-leaved. The fruits are round, beautiful, average weight 95-100 g, medium transportability. Cultivated as a repeated crop in open fields, intended for early and high-quality harvest. Suitable for fresh consumption and processing. Yield 35-40 t/ga. The fruits contain 5.7% dry matter, 2.38% sugar, 15.5 mg% ascorbic acid. Tasting score 4.7 points [20,21].

Barlos F₁ - Created in Uzbekistan. Mid-ripening (110-115 days), medium-sized, unpretentious plant. The fruits are round, large, average weight 115-130 g, firm, beautiful in appearance. One of the most common varieties in the republic. The fruits are intended for fresh consumption, processing and long-distance transportation. Tasting score 4.4 points [22].

Djina F₁ – A hybrid imported from the Netherlands. Mid-ripening, medium-tall (80-100 cm), bushy, strongly leafy, large fruits, average weight 80-110 g, red color, round, flat-round shape. Yield 45-50 t/ga. The fruits are suitable for fresh consumption and processing. The fruit contains 5.8% dry matter, 4.2% sugar, 24.1% ascorbic acid. Tasting score 4.5 points [23].

Moreliya F₁ - A hybrid imported from the Netherlands. Mid-ripening (110-115 days), medium-sized, unpretentious plant. The fruits are round, average weight 90-120 g, beautiful in appearance. The fruits are intended for fresh consumption, processing and long-distance transportation. Tasting score 4.8 points [24].

Lojayin F₁ – A hybrid imported from the Netherlands. Early mid-ripening, the growing season is 105-110 days. The plant is simple, determinant, well-leaved, 50-55 cm tall. The fruit is round, slightly ribbed on top, red, average weight 100-120 g, the fruits are intended for processing, fresh consumption, and long-distance transportation. Yield 35-40 t/ga. Tasting score 4.9 points [25].

Results and their analysis. In Uzbekistan, tomato seedlings are grown in heated and unheated film greenhouses. A high-quality soil mixture is prepared for seedling cultivation. The mixture contains 40% turf soil, 40% humus, and 20% softening materials (rice husks or sand). Pre-sorted seeds are soaked in a solution of potassium permanganate for 15-20 minutes, then washed in clean water and soaked in plain water for 12 hours. When growing seedlings without pickling, they are allocated a 7x7 cm or 8x8 cm feeding area. Seeds of zoned varieties with a purity of 98% and a germination rate of at least 85% are sown in the 1st class.

Seeds are pre-sown in water or in a 0.01-0.05% solution of growth stimulants and microelements for 10-12 hours, then treated with fungicides. Tomato seedlings were grown in open ground in a nursery near a greenhouse. 200-250 g of hybrid seeds per 1 hectare of open ground [26].

The industrial technology of tomato cultivation begins with the cultivation of high-quality seedlings. When the seedlings have five to six true leaves, they should be 25-35 cm tall. The seedlings are grown in a pinch. The seedlings are pinched out at the first leaf stage to 8x8 cm and the plants are fed twice (15-20 g of ammonium nitrate and 30-40 g of superphosphate per 10 l of water, in the second feeding these fertilizers are given in an amount of 30-40 g and 60-80 g, respectively), watered, cleaned of weeds, and when they have 6-7 true leaves, they are planted in the field. To ensure that they grow dark green, short, and strong, it is necessary to strictly adhere to the treatment technology, dosages, and timing. The seedlings are planted in the field in early July, with a denser spacing (20-25 cm) between the bushes. Yozgi muddatda takroriy ekin sifatida o‘stirilganda bizlar pomidor nav va duragaylarning tayyor ko‘chat chiqimi va sifat ko‘rsatkichlarini o‘rganib chiqdik.

Table No. 1 presents data on “Quality indicators of tomato varieties and hybrids seedlings grown for repeated planting in the summer period”. In the experiment, seeds of all tomato varieties and hybrids were sown on May 5-10. In all studied varieties and hybrids, the seedling height was 23.1 Yulduz (control) - 25.6 (Morelia F1) cm, the number of leaves was 6.2-6.7, the leaf surface area of the seedling was 190.4-211.3 cm², and the weight of one seedling was 29.9-33.6 g.

The average height of the finished seedlings was the highest in the Morelia F1 variety and hybrids (25.6 cm); 24.7 cm in the Lojain F1 variety and hybrids. In these hybrids, the number of leaves (6.7 - 6.4 pieces) and the leaf surface area (211.3 - 208.2 cm²) were also the highest, and the average weight of one seedling was also higher in these hybrids (33.6 - 32.8 g).

The shortest plants (23.1 - 23.9 cm) when growing seedlings of tomato varieties and hybrids Yulduz (control) and Djina F1 varieties and hybrids. These varieties and hybrids produced seedlings with the fewest leaves and the smallest weight.

The first treatment of tomato plants planted as a repeated crop is carried out after the seedlings have emerged - 10 days later. The thinning of seedlings is repeated after another 12 - 15 days. During the growing season, the rows are cultivated 6-7 times using KOR-4.2 cultivators. The blades are adjusted to the ridge several times. During the growing season, the soil moisture is maintained at 75-80% of the field moisture capacity.

1- table

**Quality indicators of tomato varieties and hybrids seedlings grown for repeated planting in the summer period
“Turob Bobo” farm, 2022 - 2024**

t/n	Varieties and hybrids	Seedling height, cm	Number of leaves, pcs.	Leaf surface area, cm ²	Weight of one seedling, g
1	Yulduz (control)	23,1	6,2	190,4	29,9
2	Burxon F ₁	24,2	6,4	200,5	32,1
3	Djina F ₁	23,9	6,3	199,6	30,6
4	Moreliya F ₁	25,6	6,7	211,3	33,6
5	Lojayin F ₁	24,7	6,6	208,2	32,8
6	Barlos F ₁	23,4	6,3	200,1	30,2

Figure 1. Preparing the soil for tomatoes in fields cleared of grain

During the experiment, in order to study the growth and development of tomato varieties and hybrids, phenological observations were conducted, the duration of flowering, fruiting, and the onset of fruit ripening, as well as biometric observations were conducted to determine plant height, the number of leaves per plant, the number of lateral branches per plant, and the leaf surface area per plant in selected plants from each variant.

In order to study the growth and development of plants when growing tomato varieties and hybrids as a repeated crop, phenological observations were conducted, the duration of flowering, fruiting and the onset of fruit ripening, as well as biometric observations were conducted to determine plant height, the number of leaves per plant, and the number of lateral branches per plant in selected plants from each variant.

When analyzing the data obtained, it was found that each plant had 68.8% of the total number of seedlings on September 15 compared to the variants. (Yulduz (control) – 80.4 (Morelia F1) leaves, leaf surface area per plant 2091.5-2444.2 cm², number of side branches 6.9-8.7, plant height 78.4-85.7 cm. According to the data obtained, the Morelia F1 and Lojain F1 hybrids had the highest number of leaves (80.4 and 79.7), leaf surface area per plant 2444.2 -2422.8 cm², number of side branches (8.7 and 8.4), and plant height (85.7 and 84.2 cm). In the Barlos F1 and Djina F1 hybrids, these indicators were 75.2-71.9 pieces, 2286.1-2185.6 cm² and 84.0-81.3 cm, respectively. The lowest indicators were observed in the standard variant, the number of leaves per plant was 78.4 pieces, the leaf surface area per plant was 2091.5 cm², the number of lateral branches per plant was 6.9 pieces and the plant height was 78.4.5 cm. According to the data obtained, the number of leaves, leaf surface area per plant, and number of lateral branches were the highest in the Lojain F1 and Morelia F1 hybrid plants.

Table No. 2 presents data on "Continuation of growth and development phases in tomato plants planted as a repeated crop in the summer period."

Analyzing this data, when tomatoes were grown as a repeated crop, the period from planting seedlings in the field to flowering for all studied varieties and hybrids ranged from 30 days (Morelia F1) to 33 days (Yulduz, Barlos F1). By the beginning of the harvest phase, the earliest fruit appearance among varieties and hybrids was observed on day 43 in Morelia F1, on day 44 in Lojain F1, Burkhan F1 hybrids. The latest fruiting phase

2-Figure. Increasing leaf number in tomato varieties and hybrids (2022 - 2024)

On day 46, it was observed in the Yulduz (control) and Barlos F1 hybrids. In the experiment, the occurrence of the fruiting phase in other varieties and hybrids did not differ significantly.

The earliest fruit ripening was observed in the Morelia F1 and Lojain F1 hybrids at 55-56 days after transplanting tomato seedlings. The latest first harvest was at 58 days in the Yulduz (control) and Barlos F1 varieties and hybrids.

Based on the data obtained, the varieties and hybrids that grow and develop the fastest and yield the earliest harvest when tomatoes are planted as a repeated crop in the summer period were identified as Morelia F1 and Lojain F1 hybrids.

Tomato harvest begins when the fruit is fully ripe. The main indicators of the state standard requirements for tomato fruits are as follows: “Freshly picked tomatoes” - in accordance with the requirements of GOST 1725-85, they should be freshly picked, clean, whole, ripe, of regular shape, not damaged by picking and not sunburned, and red and pink in color depending on the degree of ripeness. Products from small-fruited and elongated tomato varieties are used for conservation.

2-table

Continuation of growth and development phases in tomato plants planted as a repeated crop in the summer period

“Turob Bobo” farm, 2022 - 2024

№	Varieties and hybrids	After transplanting, in days			
		until flowering	until the harvest begins	until the first harvest	until the last harvest
1	Yulduz (control)	33	46	58	100
2	Burxon F ₁	31	44	57	108
3	Djina F ₁	32	45	57	105

4	Moreliya F ₁	30	43	55	115
5	Lojayin F ₁	31	44	56	110
6	Barlos F ₁ ,	33	46	58	102

3-Figure. Tomato growing processes in the conditions of the Samarkand region

This allows for the mixing of unripe, i.e. pink, tomatoes. The degree of ripeness of steamed tomatoes can be red, pink, brown and white.

Table 3 presents data on “Yield of promising tomato varieties and hybrids planted as a repeated crop in the summer period”. When analyzing these data, the average weight of fruits by variant was 97.2 (Dzhina F₁ – 120.2 (Barlos F₁) g. The largest fruits were obtained when growing Barlos F₁ hybrid plants (120.2 g), while in the Morelia F₁ and Lojain F₁ variants this indicator was 99.5 – 110.6 g. The average weight of fruits in the Standard (Yulduz) variant was 108.6 g.

3-table

Yield of promising tomato varieties and hybrids planted as a repeated crop in the summer period

“Turob Bobo” farm, 2022 - 2024

№	Varieties and hybrids	Average weight of fruits, g	Productivity by month, t/ga			Average productivity	
			VII	VIII	IX	t/ga	%
1	Yulduz (control)	108,6	4,89	11,41	16,30	32,6	100,0
2	Burxon F ₁	105,8	5,62	13,66	17,92	37,2	114,1
3	Djina F ₁	97,2	5,38	13,09	17,63	36,1	110,7
4	Moreliya F ₁	99,5	6,27	14,87	21,36	42,5	130,7
5	Lojayin F ₁	110,6	5,88	14,06	19,46	39,4	120,8
6	Barlos F ₁ ,	120,2	5,05	12,51	16,94	34,5	105,8

EKF₀₅=2.72 t/ga
Sx%=4,02

Tomatoes are among the plants with great potential, opportunities, strong growth, and fruits that can be harvested many times.

According to the data obtained, when tomatoes were grown as a repeated crop, the tomato yield by variant was 32.6 - 42.5 t/ha. The highest yield - 42.5 t/ha was obtained from the Morelia F1 hybrid plants. This indicator is 30.7% higher than the standard - Yulduz variant. The average yield in the Lojain F1 and Burkhan F1 variants was 39.4 - 37.2 t/ha.

In our experiment, when tomatoes were grown as a repeated crop, the yield and quality of varieties and hybrids were studied, as well as the biochemical composition of the fruit.

According to the obtained data, it was determined that the dry matter content of tomato fruit is 5.5 (Yulduz) -6.2% (Morelia F1). The highest dry matter content was observed in the Morelia F1 and Lojain F1 hybrids. This is lower in the Burkhan F1, Djina F1 and Barlos F1 hybrids.

Figure 4. Tomato hybrid Morelia F1

The indicators were 5.9; 5.7 and 5.6%, respectively. The main part of the dry matter was sugar, and the highest sugar content (2.5-3.0%) was observed in the above varieties and hybrids.

According to the experimental variants, the carotene content was 0.8-1.8 mg%. According to the data obtained, the highest carotene content in tomato fruits was determined in the Morelia F1 (1.8 mg%) and Lojain F1 (1.7 mg%) hybrids. When studying the content of vitamin "C", it was found that the fruits of the Morelia F1 hybrid contained the most vitamin "C" - 30.8 mg%, the Lojain F1 hybrid - 28.3 mg%, the Djina F1 hybrid - 28.0 mg% and the Burkhan F1 hybrid - 29.6 mg%.

When tomato varieties and hybrids were grown as a repeated crop in the summer, the highest tasting scores of fruits were observed in the fruits of the Lojayin F1 (4.9 points), Morelia F1 (4.8 points), and Burkhan F1 (4.7 points) varieties and hybrids. When determining economic efficiency, we used data from the accounting of the "Turob Bobo" farm and the "Sample technological cards for the care and production of agricultural crops (for 2022 - 2026, for vegetable, potato, melon and grape crops, 2022).

The analysis showed that in the experiments conducted on the "Turob Bobo" farm in Tayloq district, the total costs incurred when growing promising tomato varieties and hybrids as a repeated crop were 31,444,916 - 36,219,686 soums/ha compared to the options. When growing promising tomato varieties and hybrids as a repeated crop, the yield value per square meter changed from 81,043,600 soums (Yulduz) to 105,655,000 soums (Morelia F1). The average selling price of one kilogram of tomatoes was 2,486 soums, with the highest income of

105,655,000 soums/ha and the highest profitability of 191.7% obtained when growing Morelia F1 hybrid plants. For Lojain F1 and Burkhan F1 hybrid plants, these indicators were 63,223,844 - 58,567,104 soums/ha and 182.1% - 173.9%, respectively.

Figure 5. Economic efficiency of growing promising tomato varieties and hybrids as a repeated crop in the summer period (2022-2024)

The lowest income (53,068,194- 49,598,684 soums/ha) and profitability (162.3- 157.7%) were obtained when growing plants of the Barlos F1 and Yulduz varieties and hybrids.

Conclusions. When growing promising tomato varieties and hybrids as a repeated crop in the summer period, the highest quality and strongest seedlings were obtained from the Morelia F1 and Lojain F1 hybrids. The varieties and hybrids that grow and develop the fastest and yield the earliest were identified as Morelia F1 and Lojain F1 hybrids. The highest dry matter content (6.2 and 6.0 %) and the highest carotene content (1.8 mg% and 1.7 mg%) were determined in the fruit of the Morelia F1 and Lojain F1 hybrids. The yield of tomatoes by variant was 32.6 - 42.5 t/ha. The highest yield - 42.5 t/ha was obtained from the Morelia F1 hybrid plants. This indicator is 30.7% higher than the standard - Yulduz control variant. The highest income of 105,655,000 soums/ha and the highest profitability rate of 191.7% were obtained when growing Morelia F1 hybrid plants.

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